

CROP AND RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

Soils

Characteristics of Fe-toxic soils and affected plants and their correction in acid Haplaquents of Meghalaya

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Fe toxicity and its associated nutritional disorders hamper wetland rice cultivation in the Meghalaya valleys where 80% of India's rice is grown.

Fe toxicity was found in soils with one or more of these characteristics: water table < 40 cm, > 1.25% active Fe, > 2.98% organic matter, > 200 ppm soluble Fe content, < 14.3 ppm Bray's P, < 60 ppm available K, < 0.71 ppm DTPA-Cu, and pH usually below 6.0 even after 7 wk continued submergence (Table 1). Runoff from hills also contained appreciable amounts of soluble Fe and suspended organic matter.

Fe toxicity caused fewer panicles and filled grains per hill, delays in crop maturity of 20-25 d, and yield reduction of 1.0-2.0 t/ha. Critical limits of 10 ppm of P, 70 ppm of K, 2.15 ppm of Zn, and 0.71 ppm of Cu differentiated deficient soils from nondeficient ones.

We conducted field trials at the Barapani research farm to examine the response of rice to P and K on Fe-toxic Haplaquent (pH 5.05, 1.96% organic C, 2.19% active Fe, 5.98 ppm Bray's P₂-P, 42.5 ppm exchangeable K, water table < 40 cm) during the 1987-88 kharif seasons.

Soils had more than 250 ppm Fe²⁺ within 3 wk of submergence and maintained this concentration up to 70-75 d. Plants in the control plots showed Fe-toxicity symptoms about 55 d after transplanting. Grain yield response varied from 0.9 t/ha (66 kg K/ha) to

1.5 t/ha (66 kg K + 30 kg P/ha). Alleviating P and K deficiency and Fe toxicity in rice shoots may have caused this significant yield increase.

Surface drainage was impeded because a continuous supply of soluble Fe in water

came from hill slopes, upwelling, and seepage. Grain and straw uptake of K and P increased significantly over the control with all the applied treatments.

A separate trial was conducted on Fe-toxic acid Haplaquent (pH 4.9, 4.09%

Table 1. Nutrient content of Fe-toxic soils and affected plants showing varying magnitudes of toxicity symptoms in the Khasi Hills district of Meghalaya, India, 1987-88.

Particular	Toxicity symptoms ^a			
	Mild		Severe	
	Range	% deficiency	Range	% deficiency
Soil				
pH	5.1-6.0 (5.5)	—	5.1-5.9 (5.6)	—
Organic C (%)	0.9-2.9 (1.8)	47.1	1.25-6.1 (3.2)	5.9
Bray's P ₂ -P (ppm)	5.8-19.7 (9.4)	70.6	1.2-18.5 (6.2)	88.1
N-NH ₄ OAC-K (ppm)	41.0-97.0 (70.8)	29.4	41.0-136 (89.9)	19.0
DTPA-Zn (ppm)	1.57-4.23 (2.3)	35.3	1.2-3.3 (1.8)	58.3
DTPA-Cu (ppm)	0.70-3.31 (1.1)	5.9	0.4- 1.4 (0.69)	58.7
Active Fe (%)	0.66-1.08 (1.04)	11.8 (toxic)	1.9-2.8 (1.9)	100 (toxic)
Plant				
Fe (ppm)	202-487 (387)	nil	256-630 (430)	nil
Mn (ppm)	118-785 (395)	nil	130-825 (554)	nil
Zn (ppm)	31-126 (70)	24.5	27-91 (57)	52
Cu (ppm)	9.8-53 (39)	35.3	8-46 (27)	30
B (ppm)	19-53 (29)	5.9	5-51 (17)	52
P (%)	0.2-0.58 (0.02)	—	0.09-0.15 (0.08)	75
K (%)	1.1-1.7 (1.3)	—	0.09-1.5 (1.1)	26

^aFigures in parentheses indicate mean values.

Table 2. Influence of Zn and Cu on yield and mineral uptake in Fe-toxic acid Haplaquent.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Yield (t/ha)		Mineral uptake (kg/ha) by grain							
	Grain	Straw	P	K	Ca	Mg	Zn	Cu	Fe	Mn
Control	2.8	4.2	7.0	9.0	2.2	7.0	0.12	0.12	0.38	0.13
6 Zn	3.9	4.9	10.6	13.0	5.5	10.0	0.23	0.17	0.47	0.16
12 Zn	3.8	4.8	10.1	13.0	6.0	7.0	0.25	0.06	0.29	0.20
4 Cu	4.0	5.0	11.0	12.8	3.2	10.9	0.21	0.12	0.37	0.25
8 Cu	3.0	3.8	8.0	10.0	3.0	7.0	0.19	0.11	0.31	0.16
6 Zn + 4 Cu	3.6	4.7	9.0	11.0	4.9	7.0	0.19	0.15	0.35	0.31
6 Zn + 8 Cu	3.5	4.7	10.0	12.0	5.0	8.0	0.20	0.13	0.35	0.24
12 Zn + 4 Cu	3.0	4.9	10.0	11.6	5.8	7.0	0.23	0.17	0.46	0.21
12 Zn + 8 Cu	3.7	4.9	8.7	12.0	5.0	9.0	0.19	0.18	0.35	0.23
LSD (0.05)	1.0	1.0	2.1	2.6	1.2	2.4	0.05	0.03	0.08	0.06

organic C, 1.90% active Fe, 13 ppm Bray's P₁ P, 136 ppm exchangeable K, 0.66 ppm DTPA-Zn, 0.70 ppm DTPA-Cu, and water table <25 cm) to study the response of rice cultivar PP₂-34-155-7 to Zn and Cu. The greatest yield response,

1.2 t/ha, was recorded with 4 kg Cu/ha; it almost equaled the 1.1 t/ha from 12 kg Zn/ha (Table 2). The significant increase in grain uptake of Zn, Cu, Mn, P, and K over the control and the simultaneous reduction in Fe might have

led to proper nutrient balance and efficient use.

Proper use of P, K, Zn, and Cu fertilizer after soil and plant tissue tests can successfully mitigate Fe toxicity at these sites. □

Effects of P on growth and uptake of Cu and Fe in rice grown in excess Cu

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We examined the effect of increased P concentration on rice cultivar M-201 84 Biggs grown with and without excess Cu. Plants grew in a 1/4-strength Hoagland's solution with different combinations of Cu, P, and MES (2[N-Morpholine] ethanesulfonic acid). Excess Cu concentration was 0.5 mg/liter and increased P concentration was equal to full-strength Hoagland's solution. MES buffer was pH 6.0.

We grew seedlings hydroponically for 40 d: first for 15 d in a 1/2-strength Hoagland's solution and then for 25 d with five plants in each of six treatments (Table 1).

Same-sized plants were grown in 5-liter black buckets in a growth chamber

(Conviron CMP 2023) in a 16/8 h light/dark regime; temperature was 27 °C in light and 22 °C in darkness. Solutions were changed every other day; pH 6 and 70% humidity were maintained.

Plant samples were digested for 12 h at 120 °C with 2 ml HNO₃ and 1 ml H₂O₂ in a Teflon pressure chamber. Cu, Fe, and P concentrations were measured by flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (Perkin Elmer 2830).

Plants in the excess Cu solutions grew poorly (Table 1). Plants in Cu + P and Cu + MES + P solutions showed toxicity symptoms (yellow leaves, necrosis of leaf tips, stunted growth); plants in Cu + MES solution had less extensive symptoms. P appeared to increase the toxicity of excess Cu.

Leaf tips had higher Cu concentrations in the excess Cu solutions, but Cu exposure lowered Fe concentrations in leaf tips. Plants in the solutions containing Cu had higher Fe and Cu concentrations in the roots than plants not receiving Cu, suggesting synergistic uptake (Table 2).

The high Fe accumulation in roots, but low Fe concentration in leaf tips in Cu + P solution, may have resulted from coprecipitation of Fe in the cortical root layer and inhibited growth in leaf tips. MES buffer did not affect Fe, Cu, or P concentrations in leaf tips or roots. Plants grown in excess Cu solution without added P have greater biomass because of high internal P concentrations.

P concentration in leaf tips in the Cu + P and Cu + MES + P solutions were much higher than that of plants in the Cu + MES solution. High P concentration in leaf tips lowered the amount of metabolically active Fe²⁺ that could compete with heavy metals (such as Cu) for metabolically sensitive sites inside leaves. □

Fertilizer management

Integrated nitrogen management for irrigated lowland rice

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We conducted three experiments that combined organic and inorganic sources to supply the N required by lowland transplanted rice on a Typic Ustropept.

Soil had pH 8.1, soluble salt concentration 0.4 dS/m, 160 ppm alkaline KMnO₄-extractable N, 8.6 ppm 0.5 M NaHCO₃-extractable P, 135 ppm NH₄OAc-extractable K, and 0.32% organic C.

Test crops were laid out in a randomized block design with three replications: IR20 during 1988 pishanam (Oct-Feb), ADT36 during 1989 kar (Jun-

Table 1. Effect of P on size of plants in solutions containing excess Cu.^a

Treatment	Biomass (g)	Leaf length (cm)	Root dry weight (g)	Leaf dry weight (g)
Cu+MES	2.3 ± 0.1 c	53.4 ± 1.9 a	0.09 ± 0.01 b	0.29 ± 0.01 b
Cu+P	1.3 ± 0.2 e	43.9 ± 0.8 b	0.06 ± 0.005 c	0.12 ± 0.02 c
Cu+MES+P	1.7 ± 0.1 d	43.2 ± 0.6 b	0.08 ± 0.002 b	0.22 ± 0.009 bc
P+MES	2.4 ± 0.1 bc	59.4 ± 1.3 a	0.1 ± 0.006 ab	0.42 ± 0.03 a
P	2.9 ± 0.2 a	58.1 ± 3.9 a	0.1 ± 0.01 a	0.46 ± 0.04 a
MES	2.8 ± 0.1 ab	58.3 ± 3.4 a	0.1 ± 0.004 a	0.41 ± 0.02 a

^aWithin columns, mean values with the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level

Table 2. Chemical analysis of plants grown in a 1/4 strength Hoagland's solution with or without added P, Cu, or buffer (MES).

Treatment	Leaves				Roots		
	Fe (µg/g)	Cu (µg/g)	P (mg/g)	Fe/P	Fe (µg/g)	Cu (µg/g)	Fe/Cu
Cu+MES	91 ^a	44	2.0	455	4200	1630	3
Cu+P	87	49	11.5	76	7120	1370	5
Cu+MES+P	97	50	11.9	82	6250	1010	6
P+MES	107	26	7.4	145	1130	91	12
P	108	22	7.3	147	1330	97	14
MES	111	31	2.0	555	1150	124	9

^aValues are means from 5 plants in each treatment.